

Methodological work and use of Patient-Reported Outcomes data in randomised controlled trials (RCTs) in cancer: Literature reviews on current practices and guidelines.

Authors list: Abigail Machingura¹, Corneel Coens¹, Madeline Pe¹, Ahu Alanya¹, Antoine Regnault², Flora Mazerolle², Laurine Bunod², Joseph C. Cappelleri³, Mallorie H. Fiero⁴, Anders Ingelgård⁵, Sjoukje F. Oosting⁷, Alexandra Gilbert⁸, Cristian Frigoletti Catalan⁹, Tove Ragna Reksten¹⁰, Khadija Rerhou Rantell¹¹, Ralf Herold¹², Michael Schlichting⁶) *on behalf of SISAQOL-IMI WP2.*

1. European Organisation for Research and Treatment of Cancer Headquarters, Brussels, Belgium
2. Modus Outcomes SAS, Lyon, France
3. Pfizer Inc, Groton, Connecticut, USA
4. US Food and Drug Administration, Washington DC, USA
5. Boehringer Ingelheim International GmbH, Ingelheim, Germany
6. Merck Healthcare KGaA, Darmstadt, Germany
7. University of Groningen, University Medical Center Groningen, Dept. of Medical Oncology, Groningen, The Netherlands
8. University of Leeds, Clinical (Radiation) Oncology, Leeds Cancer Centre, UK
9. KU Leuven, Leuven, Belgium
10. Norwegian Medicines Agency, Oslo, Norway
11. Medicines and Healthcare products Regulatory Agency, London, United Kingdom
12. European Medicines Agency (EMA), Amsterdam, The Netherlands

Keywords: Patient-Reported Outcome; Health-Related Quality of Life; RCTs; EORTC; Estimand; Intercurrent Event

Corresponding author: Abigail Machingura, MSc., Quality of Life Department, European Organisation for Research and Treatment of Cancer, 83/11 Avenue E. Mounier, 1200 Brussels, Belgium; Tel: +32 (0) 2 774 13 14; abigail.machingura@eortc.org

Disclaimer: The views expressed in this article are the personal views of the author(s) and may not be understood or quoted as being made on behalf of or reflecting the position of the regulatory agency/agencies or organisations with which the author(s) is/are employed/affiliated.

Acknowledgements: The SISAQOL-IMI project has received funding from the Innovative Medicines Initiative (IMI) 2 Joint Undertaking under grant agreement No. 945052. This Joint Undertaking receives support from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program and the European Federation of Pharmaceutical Industries and Associations (EFPIA).

This publication reflects the views of the individual authors and should not be construed to represent official views or policies of the European Medicines Agency (EMA), the US Food and Drug Administration (FDA), US National Cancer Institute (NCI), Medicines and Healthcare products Regulatory Agency (MHRA), Institute for Quality and Efficiency in Health Care (IQWiG), Health Canada, the Norwegian Medical Products Agency (NOMA), the American Society of Clinical Oncology (ASCO) or the European Society for Medical Oncology (ESMO) or any other institution, organisation, or entity. This publication reflects the authors' view and that neither IMI nor the EU, EFPIA are responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained therein.

SISAQOL-IMI WP2 members to be listed as contributors and cited in PubMed:

First name	Last name	Organisation name	Country
Nnadozie	C Emechebe	ABBVIE	DE
Saskia	le Cessie	Leiden University	BE
Kim	Cocks	Adelphi Values	UK
Christoph	Gerlinger	Bayer AG and Gynecology, Obstetrics and Reproductive Medicine, University Medical School of Saarland, Germany	US
Yun	Su	Bayer	DE
Sonya	Eremenco	Critical Path Institute	US
Cheryl	D Coon	Critical Path Institute	US
Jammbé	Musoro	European Organisation for Research and Treatment of Cancer	BE
4Nicola Jane	Latino	European Society for Medical Oncology	CH
Molenberghs	Geert	KU Leuven	BE
Verbeke	Geert	KU Leuven	BE
Kris	Bogaerts	KU Leuven	BE
Vivek	Pawar	EMD Serono	US
Solomon	Alexi	Myeloma Patients Europe (representing WECAN)	BE
Sandra	Mitchell	National Cancer Institute	US
Kristin	Bjordal	Oslo University Hospital	NO
Paul	Cislo	Pfizer	US
Satrajit	Roychoudhury	Pfizer	US
Sarah	Boehme	Pfizer	US
Mogens	Groenvold	Region Hovedstaden	DK
Morten A	Petersen	Region Hovedstaden	DK
Anja	Schiel	Norwegian Medical Products Agency	NO
Jaap	Reijneveld	VU Amsterdam	NL
Ulrich	Grouven	Institute for Quality and Efficiency in Health Care (IQWiG)	DE
Claudia	Rutherford	University of Sydney	AU
Els	Goetghebeur	Ghent University (representing STRATOS)	BE
Olalekan Lee	Aiyegbusi	University of Birmingham	UK
Samantha	Cruz Rivera	University of Birmingham	UK
Ting-Yu	Chen	US Food and Drug Administration	US
Melanie	Calvert	University of Birmingham	UK
Cole	Ayasse	Critical Path Institute	US

44 ABSTRACT

46 **Background:**

47 Providing accurate and reliable information on favourable and unfavourable effects of an anti-cancer treatment based on health-
48 related quality-of-life (HRQoL) or other patient-reported outcomes (PROs) present specific challenges. These challenges hinder the
49 comparison of such results across clinical studies and generalisation of conclusions about patient experience with cancer treatments.
50 The SISAQOL-IMI consortium was established to develop consensus recommendations on the design, collection, analysis and
51 interpretation of PRO data in cancer clinical trials.

52 **Objectives:**

53 The objective of this research is to obtain an overview of the current practices and existing recommendations on the use of PRO
54 data in randomised controlled trials (RCTs), structured around the framework of well-defined PRO-based objectives.

56 **Methods:**

57 A literature search was conducted in PubMed, including documents from the clinicaltrials.gov and EMA websites using systematic
58 and free text terms according to PRISMA principles. Eligible sources included published protocols and assessments for randomised
59 controlled phase III cancer clinical trials, guidelines, recommendations and systematic reviews concerning PROs. Stakeholders were
60 approached to provide additional relevant documents on current practices and guidelines. Descriptive summaries included study
61 design features, PRO objectives, endpoints, intercurrent event strategies and definitions of analysis sets.

63 **Results:**

64 For the current practices, 49 source documents were reviewed including 6 systematic reviews of PRO practices, 29 protocols of
65 clinical trials, and clinical trials submitted in 14 European public assessment reports (EPARs) of authorised medicines. For current
66 guidelines, 12 methodological and 12 stakeholder guidelines were reviewed. PROs were secondary trial objectives in 97% of the
67 protocols (28/29) and 64% of the EPARs (9/14). The most frequent PRO endpoint types were magnitude of change (from baseline)
68 at specific time points (84% (41/49)) and time-to-event (72% (21/49)). The most commonly reported intercurrent events across
69 source documents were death, protocol treatment discontinuation, disease progression, deviation from protocol defined treatment,
70 and patient too ill to fill out the questionnaire. Various strategies on intercurrent event addressing were reported. 25% (6/24) of the
71 guidelines recommend imputing the worst score or a deterioration event, 8% (2/24) recommend censoring PRO score at the time of
72 death and 8% (2/24) recommend removing the patient from analysis. The definitions of analysis sets in this review varied
73 substantially among the source documents.

75 **Conclusion:**

76 Our review revealed gaps between best methodological practices for PRO collection and analysis and reveal a high level of
77 divergency among current practices. This might be partly explained by uncertainty about providing well-defined PRO objectives
78 and endpoints, lack of clarity on appropriate analysis sets and missing guidance on how to address events that need special
79 consideration to minimise potential impact on the interpretation of PRO results (e.g., death). This is evidenced by the scarcity of
80 information on strategies for addressing intercurrent events and missing data. Applying the estimand framework will provide an
81 opportunity for improving the design, conduct, analysis, and interpretation of PRO results, in particular standardisation of PRO
82 analysis so that the relevant information is clearly provided.

87 1 INTRODUCTION

88

89 The main goal of clinical trials in cancer is to evaluate the efficacy and safety of new treatments. Common endpoints
90 used for the evaluation of treatment efficacy in this context are related to benefits in terms of survival, disease
91 progression (progression-free survival) or objective response (tumour shrinkage). In addition to these outcomes
92 experienced by patients, cancer trials often seek to capture how cancer patients feel, function and experience since
93 these patients are faced with multiple symptoms from the disease itself and side effects resulting from treatments [1].
94 [2]. Disease symptoms and treatment side effects may affect the functioning and well-being of a patient causing poor
95 quality-of-life. Patient-reported outcomes (PROs) are outcomes based on a report that comes directly from the patient
96 about the status of their health condition without amendment or interpretation of their response by a clinician or
97 anyone else [3]].

98 Increasingly, PROs are being recognised as important endpoints complementary to other clinical endpoints in the
99 evaluation of new treatments [4, 5, 6, 7]. PROs are outcome measures that reflect patient's perception of the impact of
100 the disease and treatment on the physical, psychological and social aspects of daily life [8]. Typically, PROs capture
101 certain disease-related symptoms, physical function, role function, symptomatic adverse events [9] and more general
102 concepts such as health-related quality-of-life (HRQoL).

103 The demonstration of PRO benefits in the context of clinical trials raises specific challenges in terms of study design
104 (especially endpoint definition), analysis and interpretation [10, 12]. These challenges, associated with a perceived lack
105 of concrete methodological guidelines for some of these aspects, lead to a variety of analytical approaches for PRO
106 endpoints in cancer clinical trials hindering the comparison of results across clinical studies and generalisation of
107 conclusions about patient experience on cancer treatments [13, 14, 15].

108 The Setting International Standards in Analysing Patient-Reported Outcomes and Quality-of-Life Endpoints
109 (SISAQOL) was a consortium established to develop standards, guidelines, and recommendations for the analysis of
110 PRO data in Randomised Controlled Trials (RCTs) in cancer [16, 17, 18] and was awarded an innovative medicines
111 initiative (IMI) grant in 2020. The SISAQOL-IMI consortium consists of over 40 international expert stakeholders,
112 including leading PRO researchers and statisticians, and key individuals from international oncological and medical
113 societies, advisory and regulatory bodies, academic societies, pharmaceutical industry, cancer institutes, and patient
114 advocacy organisations. SISAQOL-IMI builds on existing SISAQOL work to establish recommendations on design,
115 analysis, presentation, and interpretation for PRO data in cancer clinical trials, with an expanded set of work topics,
116 including more in-depth recommendations for randomised controlled trials and single-arm studies, and for defining
117 clinically meaningful outcomes [18].

118 The initial task for the creation of the recommendations by the SISAQOL-IMI consortium was to describe the current
119 state-of-the-art of PRO practices in RCTs. The objective of this work was to provide an overview of current practices
120 and of the existing guidelines and methodological recommendations on the use of PRO data in RCTs, focusing on cancer
121 treatment structured around the framework of well-defined PRO-based objectives [17]. Concepts derived from the recent

122 estimand framework were used to review the handling of intercurrent events. This work aims to contribute to advancing
123 drug development and enhancing research practices.

124 **2 MATERIALS AND METHODS**

125 **2.2 Data Collection**

126 **2.2.1 Search strategy and selection criteria: Current Practices and Guidelines**

127 A search was conducted on PubMed, and the clinicaltrials.gov and European Medicines Agency (EMA) websites using
128 systematic and free text terms according to PRISMA 2020 principles (26). Eligible source documents were published
129 protocols of randomised controlled phase III cancer trials, guidelines, recommendations and systematic reviews
130 concerning PROs and health-related quality-of-life (HRQoL).

131 Systematic reviews: A literature search on PubMed was performed on 3 November 2020. The search terms were (quality
132 of life OR patient reported outcomes) AND (recommendations OR guidelines) AND (cancer OR oncology) AND
133 (statistical analysis). The search was done for all available relevant articles until 3 November 2020.

134
135 Protocols: Another search was conducted on clinicaltrials.gov 4 November 2020 to identify protocols for clinical trials
136 that assessed PROs. We searched for phase III oncology studies from 2016 to 2020 where the study protocol was
137 available online. We furthered the search using the filter terms (cancer) AND (quality of life) OR (patient reported
138 outcomes). Forty-one clinical trials were identified with their respective protocols.

139
140 European public assessment reports (EPARs): To provide complementary information, we conducted a search on the
141 EMA website on 2 November 2020 for relevant EPARs, that is for assessment reports and summaries of product
142 characteristics of medicines. These documents include descriptions of clinical trials as they were submitted for
143 assessment. The search focused on authorised medicines in the human category from 2018 to 2020. When a clinical trial
144 description was included in an EPAR document and available as a protocol (above), it was counted only once.

145
146 Guidelines: Stakeholders (Academic, Industry, Non-profit Cancer Organisations, Regulators, Health Technology
147 Assessment (HTA), small and medium-sized enterprises (SME)/contract research organisation (CRO), Patient
148 representatives) were approached to provide relevant literature for the current practices and current guidelines. These
149 included guidelines from the Food and Drug Administration (FDA), the EMA, the International Council for
150 Harmonisation of Technical Requirements for Registration of Pharmaceuticals for Human Use (ICH), HTA, PRO
151 consortium guidance and other methodological guidelines such as SPIRIT-PRO and CONSORT-PRO.

152 153 **Data extraction**

154
155 The screening and data extraction were performed by two independent investigators (AM, MPe).

156 Systematic reviews: The information that was extracted included i) well-defined PRO objectives that can be matched
157 with analysis methods. This takes into account identifying the between-groups PRO objectives (superiority, non-
158 inferiority, descriptive/exploratory) and translating them into target estimands; ii) design considerations for PRO-based
159 endpoints; this takes into account identifying the timing and frequency of PRO assessments (including baseline), while

160 balancing the need for assessments at clinically relevant time points and reducing patient burden; iii) PRO data quality;
161 this takes into account setting criteria to assess quality of collected PRO data, ensuring that there is enough quality data
162 available to respond to the PRO-based objectives.

163 Protocols & EPARs: For current PRO practices (ascertained through published protocols and EPARs), information
164 extracted from the publications included PRO objective, type of PRO endpoint, patient reported outcome measure
165 (PROM) used, cancer site, whether or not treatment was clearly defined, clearly stated comparison of PROs between
166 treatment arms, PRO endpoint of interest, population level summary, clinical relevance threshold, sensitivity analysis
167 for PROs, calculation of completion rates, intercurrent events (ICE) and how they were handled, timing and frequency
168 of PRO assessments, use of time windows, assessment of PROs after treatment or after progression/treatment
169 discontinuation, clearly defined valid PRO numerator or denominator used in the calculation of completion rates. If
170 ICEs are not clearly stated, ICEs were inferred from the reasons for treatment discontinuation occurring before the
171 endpoint is reached.

172 Guidelines: Considering current methodological guidelines, the aim was to extract the current recommendations on
173 analysis of PRO data. This included guidelines on the extracted information from the current practices as well as data
174 quality.

176 **2.3 Data analysis**

177 Descriptive data analysis was performed for all the included sources. Qualitative variables were reported using
178 frequencies (absolute numbers) and percentages. Quantitative variables were reported using mean and range.

179
180

3 FINDINGS

3.1 Selection

An overview of the selection process is provided in Figure 1.

Protocols, EPARs and systematic reviews: For the current practices, 41 protocols and 77 EPAR documents (descriptions of clinical trials submitted for assessment) were extracted. These were screened through title and abstract review; 67 source documents were passed for full text review. Overall, 49 source documents, including 29 protocols, 14 EPARs, and 6 systematic reviews provided as references from stakeholders (table 1 appendix), were reviewed for current practices.

Guidelines: For the current guidelines, 1070 source documents were extracted from PubMed and 100 key methodological recommendations/references provided by SISAQOL-IMI stakeholders. Fifty-six of these passed for full text review. Subsequently, 24 source documents were reviewed for current guidelines, including 12 of them methodological and 12 stakeholder (table 1 appendix).

3.2 Current practices: Characteristics of the source documents

Protocols, EPARs and systematic reviews: Of the 49 sources in this review for current practices, 29 were protocols from phase III RCTs, 14 were EPARs and 6 systematic reviews (see Table 1). These included more than 10 different cancer types. Most of the protocols and EPARs reported HRQoL outcomes as secondary endpoints (37/43, Table 1) and the remaining included HRQoL as exploratory or did not indicate its role; no study with HRQoL as primary endpoint was identified. The sample size ranged from 20 to 2840 patients.

3.2.1 PRO research objectives and design

Protocols, EPARs and systematic reviews: Seventy-six percent (37/49) of the source documents reported including PRO as a secondary objective, and 95% (35/37) of these had PROs included as part of the approach for testing multiple hypotheses in a confirmatory trial aiming for confirmatory superiority objective. This was defined by a clearly stated PRO objective and hypothesis for a confirmatory PRO endpoint. Thirty-seven percent (18/49) used PRO outcomes as a descriptive or exploratory objective (see Table 2).

Different types of analysis sets and numerous variations of the definition of the intention to treat (ITT) in the analysis of PRO data were reported (Table 4). The most used analysis set was all randomised patients with baseline assessment form and at least one PRO follow-up form (35% (15/43)). Twenty-two percent (11/49) of the source documents mentioned the use of all randomised patients as the PRO analysis set. Fourteen percent (7/49) used the safety analysis set and 4% (2/49) reported the use of all randomised patients with baseline PRO assessment. Eighteen percent (9/49) did not indicate the analysis set used.

3.2.2 Endpoint types and analysis methods

Protocols, EPARs and systematic reviews: The most commonly used endpoint type was magnitude of change (change from baseline) at specific time points (84% (41/49)) (see Table 2). Time-to-event endpoints were the second most used (43% (21/49)) and 95% (20/21) of these were time-to-deterioration. Eighteen percent (9/49) of the source documents reported responder (proportion of patients who improved, were stable or worsened) at a specific time point as an endpoint. Twelve percent (6/49) reported the use of PRO scores over time as an endpoint. These consisted of response

219 patterns or profiles over time, area under the curve, mean/median over time, worst/best score over time and last available
220 score over time. Six percent (3/49) did not mention the type of endpoint used in the analysis of PROs.

221 **3.2.3 Intercurrent events and their handling**

222 Protocols, descriptions of clinical trials submitted for assessment (EPARs) and systematic reviews: ICEs were
223 extrapolated based on the reasons for treatment discontinuation occurring before the endpoint is reached. The commonly
224 identified ICEs consisted of death, protocol treatment discontinuation, disease progression, deviation from protocol
225 defined treatment and too ill to fill out the questionnaire. Based on the analysis descriptions we retrospectively tried to
226 attribute to certain ICE strategies with some uncertainty.

227 Common ICE strategies for addressing death (forty-nine percent (24/49) of the source documents) suggested use of
228 observed data (Table 3) which can be attributed to a while-alive strategy or while-on-treatment strategy. This strategy
229 could be assumed also when removing patients from analyses. Twenty-seven percent (13/49) censored at the time of
230 death, indicating a hypothetical strategy, which could also be applicable when last-observation-carried-forward
231 approaches were used to replace the missing observation. A composite strategy might be assigned, when imputing the
232 worst PRO score for death. Twenty-two percent (11/49) did not indicate how death was handled.

233 For addressing protocol treatment discontinuation, disease progression and deviation from protocol defined treatment
234 occurring before endpoint is reached, most source documents mentioned continuing collection of PRO data and
235 including assessments after ICE in the analysis, suggesting a treatment policy approach for addressing these ICEs. The
236 second most reported approach was the use of growth curves or mixed models indicative of a hypothetical strategy, also
237 when censoring at the time of ICE, or using last-observation carried forward method. Some of the approaches included
238 use of simple imputation techniques such as imputing average score, imputing worst score, which can be considered as
239 composite strategy or removing the patient from the analysis (while-on-treatment strategy). More details on the ICE are
240 listed in Table 3.

241 **3.3 Current guidelines**

242 Guidelines: From the current guidelines (24), 12 were methodological and 12 were stakeholder guidelines (see Tables
243 2-4). Ninety-six percent (23/24) provided recommendations for the confirmatory PRO objectives. This included
244 superiority objective (13/23), non-inferiority objective (5/23) and not clearly stated confirmatory PRO objective (12/23).
245 Sixty-three percent (15/24) provided recommendations for the PROs as descriptive or exploratory endpoints.

246 On the endpoint types, the recommendations were provided mostly for the magnitude of change endpoints (83%
247 (20/24)). The focus was on change from baseline (14/20), percentage change from baseline (1/20) and absolute scores
248 (9/20). Forty-six percent (11/24) provided recommendations on the time-to-event PRO endpoints. The
249 recommendations were specifically on time-to-deterioration (5/11), time-to-improvement (1/11), time-to-stable state
250 (1/11) and unspecified time-to-event (5/11). Fifty-four percent of the guidelines (13/24) provided recommendations on
251 response at specific time points and 13% (3/24) on absolute PRO scores over time.

252
253 Regarding addressing death as an intercurrent event, 25% (6/24) of the guidelines recommend imputing the worst score
254 or a deterioration event, 8% (2/24) recommend censoring PRO score at the time of death and 8% (2/24) recommend
255 removing the patient from analysis. In the event of treatment discontinuation, disease progression, deviation from
256 protocol-defined treatment regimen or being too ill to fill out the questionnaire, the most recommended technique was

257 to continue collecting PRO data and include these assessments in the analysis. The most recommended PRO analysis
258 sets were all randomised patients (8/24), all (randomised) patients who are eligible for PRO assessments (not part of
259 trial eligibility criteria, but part of PRO-specific eligibility criteria) (6/24), all eligible patients for the trial (with no
260 inclusion of PRO-specific eligibility criteria) (5/24) and all (randomised) patients who received at least one dose of the
261 treatment.

263 **4 DISCUSSION**

264 This study provides an overview on the current practices as well as existing guidelines and methodological
265 recommendations on the use of PRO data in RCTs. We identified gaps and weaknesses in the current practices and
266 guidelines on PRO analysis, reporting and interpretation. This is evidenced by the lack of information on ICE and
267 effective ways of addressing them. There was no clear distinction between ICEs and missing data in the current
268 practices. This has a significant impact on the analysis and interpretation of PRO findings and estimates. A
269 prospective plan to collect informative reasons why intended PRO data were not collected may help to distinguish
270 between ICEs and missing data, leading to improved analysis, choice of sensitivity analysis and interpretation [19].

271
272 Most of the documents lacked clarity on PRO objectives despite having HRQoL stated as part of the approach for testing
273 multiple hypotheses for phase III RCTs in a confirmatory trial. The estimand framework was only recently formalised
274 and came into force for clinical research. According to the ICH E9 (R1) addendum [19] and other source documents
275 [20, 21, 22], the design of the trial evaluating treatment effect should be aligned with the estimands that reflect the trial
276 objectives. Different stakeholders may have different research questions of interest, and this will impact the choice of
277 the PRO estimands. This therefore calls for more consistent use of methodology, terminology and reporting of the target
278 estimands and corresponding attributes to improve standardisation across cancer research which will hopefully lead to
279 a higher impact of PRO data and less research waste.

280
281 Given the fact that the estimand framework was established only recently, ICEs were not expected to be clearly reported
282 in all the reviewed source documents. For example, 24 out of 43 protocols and descriptions of clinical trials submitted
283 for assessment (EPARs) mentioned the use of observed data only as a way of addressing death as an intercurrent event
284 which can be attributed to a while-alive strategy or while-on-treatment strategy. Some reported removing patient data
285 from the analysis, imputing the worst score, and last observation carried forward to handle death in the analysis of PRO
286 data. Corresponding to a treatment policy strategy, PRO data were continually collected and included as assessments
287 after ICE in the analysis, in order to address protocol treatment discontinuation, disease progression and deviation from
288 protocol defined treatment before the PRO endpoint. Clearly stating and defining recommendations on ICEs and
289 strategies for addressing them would provide clarity on the treatment effect estimates, improve the analysis of PRO data,
290 and facilitate comparative evaluations.

291 The most frequently reported PRO outcomes in the review were magnitude of change, specifically change from baseline,
292 and time-to-event. This was the case also in the review by Pe et al (2018) [8]. Mixed effects models for repeated
293 measures were the most commonly used and reported techniques for estimating magnitude of change outcomes.
294 However, these methods may be challenging to implement when death events occur. Also censoring due to death
295 assumes that data after death could have been observed after a death event which is implausible as data after death which

296 is a terminal event do not exist. Lack of information on how death is handled and which underlying assumptions are
297 considered for the respective methods, whether supplementary or sensitivity analysis are conducted to assess the
298 robustness of the outcome, will add uncertainty to the conclusions drawn from the analyses. Hence, reporting such
299 information will strengthen the analyses and aid the interpretation for the study results [17, 21]. There was scarce
300 mentioning of supplementary or sensitivity analyses in the papers reviewed. These approaches are useful in
301 strengthening the analysis and assessing the robustness of the study results by evaluating the extent to which the
302 conclusion of interest is impacted by varying missing data assumptions mechanisms or varying the definition of
303 estimators and strategies for addressing intercurrent events.

304
305 Time-to-event outcomes, and specifically time to deterioration, were the second most reported type of PRO outcome.
306 There was no standard definition of time-to-deterioration reported and different magnitudes of deterioration were
307 employed. PRO time-to-event endpoint is known to pose difficulties in the analysis [12, 14]. The deterioration in QoL
308 was referred to as time-to-deterioration or time-to-worsening or time-to-QoL symptom/function deterioration in some
309 source documents. The threshold used to identify a deterioration event was not clearly stated. The available guidelines
310 were not found to be highly explicit on how to clearly define a time-to-event PRO endpoint and the use of thresholds.

311
312 The findings showed analytical limitations due to frequency of assessments, variability of follow-up times between
313 treatment arms, and the feasibility to assess PRO after treatment discontinuation. Some source documents reported
314 continuous collection of PRO data after treatment discontinuation, and some reported not doing so. The majority of the
315 source documents did not report what would happen in case of treatment discontinuation for example due to disease
316 progression. Furthermore, most guidelines did not specifically address what should be done in the presence of treatment
317 discontinuation and how to analyse collected PROs after treatment discontinuation, while consistency on how treatment
318 discontinuations are handled in the analysis which would improve comparisons of the trial findings.

319
320 Although the ITT analysis population is usually the most clinically relevant and represents results based on how patients
321 present in real-world settings [29], the definition of the analysis sets in this review varied from study to study. The
322 majority of the source documents reported using the modified ITT, with different definitions used and safety population
323 to answer almost similar research questions. As different analysis populations answer different types of research
324 questions and estimands, it is important to have consistent terminology and definitions to avoid potential bias from the
325 selection of various groups of trial participants and for easier comparison of the findings.

326
327 In conclusion, this overview on current practices shows opportunities to improve the methodological quality, the
328 consistent terminology and the transparency of PRO research questions and estimands in clinical trials to address the
329 study objective(s), in particular ICEs and their addressing strategies. This includes providing details of analytical
330 approaches including, but not limited to, definitions of analysis populations and missing data approaches. This would
331 enhance the robustness, understanding and reporting of PRO results that would facilitate comparative insights on patient
332 experience in oncology and could also facilitate the use of PRO outcomes by regulatory bodies in decision and policy
333 making. The use of longitudinal models and descriptive analysis will be useful in both confirmatory and descriptive
334 settings. Conducting sensitivity and supplementary analysis is encouraged as they play vital roles in strengthening the
335 analysis and findings of the PRO data. These findings will inform the development of SISAQOL-IMI consensus
336 recommendations for RCTs.

5 References

1. Velikova G, Coens C, Efficace F, Greimel E, Groenvold M, Johnson C, Singer S, van de Poll-Franse L, Young T, Bottomley A, Health-Related Quality of Life in EORTC clinical trials — 30 years of progress from methodological developments to making a real impact on oncology practice, *European Journal of Cancer Supplements*, Volume 10, Issue 1, 2012, Pages 141-149, ISSN 1359-6349, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1359-6349\(12\)70023-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1359-6349(12)70023-X).
2. Fan G, Filipczak L, Chow E. Symptom clusters in cancer patients: a review of the literature. *Curr Oncol* 2007;14(5):173e9. <https://doi.org/10.3747/co.2007.145>.
3. The U.S. Food and Drug Administration (FDA) and the National Institutes of Health (NIH) are joint sponsors of the BEST (Biomarkers, EndpointS, and other Tools) Resource. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK326791/>
4. Teixeira MM, Borges FC, Ferreira PS, Rocha J, Sepodes B and Torre C (2022) A review of patient-reported outcomes used for regulatory approval of oncology medicinal products in the European Union between 2017 and 2020. *Front. Med.* 9:968272. doi: 10.3389/fmed.2022.968272
5. Gnanasakthy A, Norcross L, DeMuro Romano C, Carson RT. A Review of Patient-Reported Outcome Labeling of FDA-Approved New Drugs (2016-2020): Counts, Categories, and Comprehensibility. *Value Health.* 2022 Apr;25(4):647-655. doi: 10.1016/j.jval.2021.10.006. *Epub* 2021 Dec 24. PMID: 35365309.
6. Fiteni F, Westeel V, Pivot X, Borg C, Vernerey D, Bonnetain F. Endpoints in cancer clinical trials. *J Visceral Surg* 2014;151(1): 17e22. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jvisc Surg.2013.10.001>.
7. US Food and Drug Administration. Patient-reported outcome measures: use in medical product development to support labeling claims; 2009. <https://www.fda.gov/media/77832/download>. Accessed 12 Feb 2021.
8. Pe et al. Statistical analysis of patient-reported outcome data in randomised controlled trials of locally advanced and metastatic breast cancer: a systematic review: *Lancet* 2018.
9. Kluetz PG, Papadopoulos EJ, Johnson LL, Donoghue M, Kwitkowski VE, Chen WH, Sridhara R, Farrell AT, Keegan P, Kim G, Pazdur R. Focusing on Core Patient-Reported Outcomes in Cancer Clinical Trials-Response. *Clin Cancer Res.* 2016 Nov 15;22(22):5618. doi: 10.1158/1078-0432.CCR-16-2140. PMID: 28151715; PMCID: PMC5895452.
10. Bottomley A, Pe M, Sloan J, et al. Analysing data from patient-reported outcome and quality of life endpoints for cancer clinical trials: a start in setting international standards. *Lancet Oncol* 2016; 17: e510–14.
11. Bonnetain F, Fiteni F, Efficace F, Anota A. Statistical challenges in the analysis of health-related quality of life in cancer clinical trials. *J Clin Oncol.* 2016;34:1953–6.
12. Fiero MH, Roydhouse JK, Bhatnagar V, Chen TY, King-Kallimanis BL, Tang S, et al. Time to deterioration of symptoms or function using patient-reported outcomes in cancer trials. *Lancet Oncol.* 2022;23:e229–34.
13. Rivera, S.C., Kyte, D.G., Aiyegbusi, O.L. et al. The impact of patient-reported outcome (PRO) data from clinical trials: a systematic review and critical analysis. *Health Qual Life Outcomes* 17, 156 (2019). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12955-019-1220-z>.
14. Anota A, Hamidou Z, Paget-Bailly S, et al. Time to health-related quality of life score deterioration as a modality of longitudinal analysis for health-related quality of life studies in oncology: do we need RECIST for quality of life to achieve standardization? *Qual Life Res* 2015;24(1):5e18. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11136-013-0583-6>.

- 378 15. Wang C, Scharfstein DO, Colantuoni E, Girard TD, Yan Y. Inference in randomized trials with death and
379 missingness. *Biometrics*. 2017;73:431–40.
- 380 16. Bottomley A, Pe M, Sloan J, Basch E, Bonnetain F, Calvert M, Campbell A, Cleeland C, Cocks K, Collette L,
381 Dueck AC, Devlin N, Flechtner HH, Gotay C, Greimel E, Griebisch I, Groenvold M, Hamel JF, King M, Kluetz
382 PG, Koller M, Malone DC, Martinelli F, Mitchell SA, Moinpour CM, Musoro JZ, O'Connor D, Oliver K, Piauxt-
383 Louis E, Piccart M, Pimentel FL, Quinten C, Reijneveld JC, Schürmann C, Smith AW, Soltys KM, Sridhara R,
384 Taphoorn MJB, Velikova G, Coens C. Moving forward toward standardizing analysis of quality of life data in
385 randomized cancer clinical trials. *Clin Trials*. 2018 Dec;15(6):624-630. doi: 10.1177/1740774518795637. Epub
386 2018 Aug 24. PMID: 30141714.
- 387 17. Coens C, Pe M, Dueck AC, Sloan J, Basch E, Calvert M, Campbell A, Cleeland C, Cocks K, Collette L, Devlin
388 N, Dorme L, Flechtner HH, Gotay C, Griebisch I, Groenvold M, King M, Kluetz PG, Koller M, Malone DC,
389 Martinelli F, Mitchell SA, Musoro JZ, O'Connor D, Oliver K, Piauxt-Louis E, Piccart M, Quinten C, Reijneveld
390 JC, Schürmann C, Smith AW, Soltys KM, Taphoorn MJB, Velikova G, Bottomley A; Setting International
391 Standards in Analyzing Patient-Reported Outcomes and Quality of Life Endpoints Data Consortium.
392 International standards for the analysis of quality-of-life and patient-reported outcome endpoints in cancer
393 randomised controlled trials: recommendations of the SISAQOL Consortium. *Lancet Oncol*. 2020
394 Feb;21(2):e83-e96. doi: 10.1016/S1470-2045(19)30790-9. PMID: 32007209.
- 395 18. Pe M, Alanya A, Sorum F R, Amdal C D, Bjordal K, Chang J, et al. Setting International Standards in Analyzing
396 Patient-Reported Outcomes and Quality of Life Endpoints in Cancer Clinical Trials-Innovative Medicines
397 Initiative (SISAQOL-IMI): stakeholder views, objectives, and procedures. *The Lancet Oncology*, Volume 24,
398 Issue 6, e270 – e283. doi: 10.1016/S1470-2045(23)00157-2.
- 399 19. International Council for Harmonisation of Technical Requirements for pharmaceuticals for human use.
400 Addendum on estimands and sensitivity analysis in clinical trials to the guideline on statistical principles for
401 clinical trials. 2019. https://database.ich.org/sites/default/files/E9-R1_Step4_Guideline_2019_1203.pdf.
402 Accessed 12 Feb 2021; E9:(R1).
- 403 20. Fiero MH, Pe M, Weinstock C, King-Kallimanis BL, Komo S, Klepin HD, et al. Demystifying the estimand
404 framework: a case study using patient-reported outcomes in oncology. *Lancet Oncol*. 2020;21:e488–94.
- 405 21. Sakamaki, K., Kawahara, T. Statistical methods and graphical displays of quality of life with survival outcomes
406 in oncology clinical trials for supporting the estimand framework. *BMC Med Res Methodol* **22**, 259 (2022).
407 <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12874-022-01735-1>
- 408 22. Lawrance R, Degtyarev E, Griffiths P, Trask P, Lau H, D'Alessio D, Griebisch I, Wallenstein G, Cocks K,
409 Rufibach K. What is an estimand & how does it relate to quantifying the effect of treatment on patient-reported
410 quality of life outcomes in clinical trials? *J Patient Rep Outcomes*. 2020 Aug 24;4(1):68. doi: 10.1186/s41687-
411 020-00218-5. PMID: 32833083; PMCID: PMC7445213.
- 412 23. Bantug ET, Coles T, Smith KC, Snyder CF, Rouette J, Brundage MD, et al. Graphical displays of patient-
413 reported outcomes (PRO) for use in clinical practice: what makes a pro picture worth a thousand words? *Patient*
414 *Educ Couns*. 2016;99:483–90.
- 415 24. Kluetz PG, O'Connor DJ, Soltys K. Incorporating the patient experience into regulatory decision making in the
416 USA, Europe, and Canada. *The Lancet Oncology*, Volume 19, Issue 5, 2018, Pages e267-e274, ISSN 1470-
417 2045, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1470-2045\(18\)30097-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1470-2045(18)30097-4).

- 418 25. ICH reflection paper - proposed ICH Guideline work to advance patient focused drug development
419 EMA/CHMP/ICH/338534/2021
- 420 26. Page MJ, McKenzie JE, Bossuyt PM, et al. The PRISMA 2020 statement: an updated guideline for reporting
421 systematic reviews. *BMJ* 2021; 372 doi: <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.n71>.
- 422 27. ICH Guideline work to advance patient focused drug development. EMA/CHMP/ICH/338534/2021. [ICH
423 reflection paper - proposed ICH Guideline work to advance Patient Focused Drug Development \(PFDD\)
424 \(europa.eu\)](#).
- 425 28. Patient-Focused Drug Development: Incorporating Clinical Outcome Assessments Into Endpoints For
426 Regulatory Decision-Making. Guidance for Industry, Food and Drug Administration Staff, and Other
427 Stakeholders. U.S. Department of Health and Human Services Food and Drug Administration April 2023.
428 [Patient-Focused Drug Development: Incorporating Clinical Outcome Assessments Into Endpoints For
429 Regulatory Decision-Making \(fda.gov\)](#).
- 430 29. Evans S, Rubin DB, Powers JH, Follmann D. Analysis Populations in Anti-Infective Clinical Trials: Whom to
431 Analyze? *Stat Commun Infect Dis*. 2018 Dec;10(1):20170002. doi: 10.1515/scid-2017-0002. Epub 2018 Aug
432 29. PMID: 30923606; PMCID: PMC6433381.
- 433
- 434

435 6 Tables and figures

436

437 **Table 1: Current practices**

CURRENT PRACTICES	Protocols (29)	EPARs (14)
Masking	n (%)	n (%)
Blinded (patient level)	14 (48%)	8 (57%)
Open Label	15 (52%)	6 (43%)
PROs included as		
Secondary Endpoint	28 (97%)	9 (64%)
Exploratory/Descriptive	7 (24%)	6 (43%)
Not reported	1 (3%)	1 (7%)
Number of participants in the trial		
Range	20 - 1150	371 - 2840
Study status		
active, not recruiting	18 (62%)	10 (71%)
completed	3 (10%)	4 (29%)
terminated prematurely	6 (21%)	-
recruiting	2 (7%)	-
Cancer types		
Bladder cancer	1 (3%)	-
Breast cancer	2 (7%)	5 (36%)
Colorectal cancer	2 (7%)	-
Kidney cancer	1 (3%)	-
Lung cancer (non-small cell)	10 (34%)	2 (14%)
Leukemia	1 (3%)	2 (14%)
Liver cancer	1 (3%)	-
Lymphoma	-	1 (7%)
Melanoma	3 (10%)	1 (7%)
Multiple myeloma	2 (7%)	-
Ovarian/peritoneal cancer	3 (10%)	1 (7%)
Prostate cancer	1 (3%)	2 (14%)
Sarcoma	2 (7%)	-
PRO measure used		
EORTC QLQ-C30	7 (24%)	2 (14%)
EQ-5D-5L	5 (17%)	6 (43%)
QLQ-C30+EQ-5D-5L	16 (55%)	6 (43%)
Others	1 (3%)	-

438

439

Table 2: PRO objectives and endpoints of interest

PRO OBJECTIVES AND ENDPOINT TYPES¹	Current Practices (49) (Protocols/EPARs/Systematic Reviews)	Current Guidelines (Methodological/ Stakeholder) (24)
Broad PRO objective		
Confirmatory (unspecified, superiority, non-inferiority)	35	23
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> unspecified superiority non-inferiority /equivalence 	4 29 -	12 13 5
Descriptive/exploratory	18	15
Endpoint type		
Time to event	21	11
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> time to event (unspecified) time to deterioration time to improvement time to stable state 	1 20 1 -	5 5 1 1
Magnitude at specific time points	41	20
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> change from baseline % change from baseline absolute scores 	38 - 11	14 1 9
Responder at specific time points	9	13
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> responder (unspecified) responder (improved) responder (stable) responder (worsened) responder (improved, stable, worsened) rate of symptom palliation (improved, stable or worsened) 	1 3 - 3 3 1	8 1 2 - 3 -
PRO score over time	6	3
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> response patterns/profiles over time area under the curve over time mean/median over time worst score over time best score over time last available score over time 	4 3 1 - - -	8 4 5 3 2 1
Not reported	3	-

¹ - source documents/guidelines can have more than one objective/endpoint. The numbers may not add to the total number of current practices or guidelines.

Table 3: Intercurrent events and how they were handled at analysis stage

Intercurrent events and how they were handled²		
Intercurrent Event	Current Practices (49) (Protocols/EPARs/Systematic Reviews)	Current Guidelines (Methodological/ Stakeholder) (24)
Death (death occurs before endpoint is reached)		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> patient is removed from analysis 	3	2
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> impute as worst score or consider as a deterioration event 	4	6
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> last observation carried forward (impute the last observation before death) 	1	1
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> use observed data only 	24	1
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> censored at the time of death 	13	2
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> not reported 	11	
Protocol treatment discontinuation (occurs before endpoint is reached)		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> continue collecting PRO data and include the assessment [after treatment discontinuation] in analysis 	24	10
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> patient is removed from analysis 	3	3
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> impute as worst score or consider as a deterioration event 	1	1
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> last observation carried forward (impute the last observation before treatment discontinuation) 	1	1
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> using growth curve analysis or mixed models (or using observed data from all patients to (implicitly) impute values) 	19	N/A
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> multiple imputation 	1	N/A
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> other simple imputation strategies (impute average score) 	2	N/A

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● censored at the time of treatment discontinuation 	13	N/A
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● not reported 	12	N/A
Disease progression (occurs before endpoint is reached)		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● continue collecting PRO data and include the assessment [after disease progression] in analysis 	23	6
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● patient is removed from analysis 	1	3
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● impute as worst score or consider as a deterioration event 	1	1
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● using growth curve analysis or mixed models (or using observed data from all patients to (implicitly) impute values) 	17	1
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● other simple imputation strategies (impute average score) 	2	N/A
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● censored at the time of disease progression 	13	N/A
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● not reported 	7	N/A
Deviation from protocol-defined treatment regimen (e.g., Start of new/subsequent therapy/use of concomitant medication or assisted devices, non-adherence, treatment switching)		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● continue collecting PRO data and include the assessment [after start of new therapy] in analysis 	22	4
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● patient is removed from analysis 	1	1
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● impute as worst score or consider as a deterioration event 	1	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● using growth curve analysis or mixed models (or using observed data from all patients to (implicitly) impute values) 	17	1

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> other simple imputation strategies (impute average score) 	2	N/A
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> censored at the time of start of new therapy 	11	N/A
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> not reported 	10	N/A
Patient too ill to fill out questionnaire		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> patient is removed from analysis 	N/A	5
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> last observation carried forward (impute the last observation before patient was too ill) 	N/A	1
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> using growth curve analysis or mixed models (or using observed data from all patients to (implicitly) impute values) 	N/A	1
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> using growth curve analysis or mixed models 	N/A	1
Unspecified (general) intercurrent event (intercurrent event occurs before endpoint is reached)		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> using growth curve analysis or mixed models by using observed data 	N/A	2
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> analysis under missing at random assumption 	N/A	1
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> report intercurrent events as a separate category in responder analysis 	N/A	1
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> last observation carried forward (impute the last observation before intercurrent event) 	N/A	1
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> other simple imputation strategies (impute average score) 	N/A	2
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Composite endpoint 	N/A	2

444 ² – source documents/guidelines can have more than one reported way of addressing intercurrent events. The numbers may not
445 add to the total number of current practices or guidelines.

446

Table 4: Analysis sets

PRO ANALYSIS SETS ³	CURRENT PRACTICES (49) (PROTOCOLS/EPARs/SYSTEMATIC REVIEWS)	CURRENT GUIDELINES (METHODODOLOGICAL/ STAKEHOLDER) (24)
All Enrolled Patients in The Trial		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> all enrolled patients in the trial (in general) 	-	1
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> all eligible patients for the trial (with no inclusion of PRO-specific eligibility criteria) 	-	5
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> all eligible patients for the trial (with completed baseline PRO assessments as part of trial eligibility criteria) 	-	3
Intent-To-Treat (ITT) Population - Definition		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> all randomised patients 	16	8
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> all (randomised) patients who are eligible for PRO assessments (not part of trial eligibility criteria, but part of PRO-specific eligibility criteria) 	1	6
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> all (randomised) patients who reached a certain PRO score at baseline 	1	2
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> all (randomised) patients with baseline PRO assessment 	2	4
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> all (randomised) patients with baseline and at least one PRO FU assessment 	19	4
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> all (randomised) patients who have at least one PRO assessment 	2	3
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> all (randomised) patients who were included in the PRO analysis 	-	3
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> modified ITT (unspecified) 	-	1
Safety Population definition:		

• All (randomised) patients who received at least one dose of the treatment	-	5
• All (randomised) patients who received at least one dose of the treatment and had non-missing PRO assessments	1	-
• All (randomised) patients who completed at least 1 baseline assessment followed by at least 1 PRO assessment after 1 dose of study drug	1	-
• All (randomised) patients who received at least one dose, with baseline PRO assessment	1	2
• All (randomised) patients who received at least one dose, with baseline & at least one PRO FU assessment	4	-
Not indicated	9	-

448 ³ – source documents/guidelines can have more than one reported way of addressing intercurrent events. The numbers may not
449 add to the total number of current practices or guidelines.

450

451

452 **CONSORT flow diagram**

464 **Figure 1:** Consort flow chart showing inclusion and exclusion criteria of the source documents for the current practices and guidelines.
 465 PROs=Patient reported outcomes. EPARs=European public assessment reports.

Appendix

Table 1

Protocols		
NCT number	Title	URL
NCT02588261	A Study of ASP8273 vs. Erlotinib or Gefitinib in First-line Treatment of Patients With Stage IIIB/IV Non-small Cell Lung Cancer Tumors With EGFR Activating Mutations	https://ClinicalTrials.gov/show/NCT02588261
NCT03066778	A Study of Pembrolizumab (MK-3475) in Combination With Etoposide/Platinum (Cisplatin or Carboplatin) for Participants With Extensive Stage Small Cell Lung Cancer (MK-3475-604/KEYNOTE-604)	https://ClinicalTrials.gov/show/NCT03066778
NCT03033511	A Study of Rovalpituzumab Tesirine as Maintenance Therapy Following First-Line Platinum-Based Chemotherapy in Participants With Extensive Stage Small Cell Lung Cancer (MERU)	https://ClinicalTrials.gov/show/NCT03033511
NCT02928224	Study of Encorafenib + Cetuximab Plus or Minus Binimetinib vs. Irinotecan/Cetuximab or Infusional 5-Fluorouracil (5-FU)/Folinic Acid (FA)/Irinotecan (FOLFIRI)/Cetuximab With a Safety Lead-in of Encorafenib + Binimetinib + Cetuximab in Patients With BRAF V600E-mutant Metastatic Colorectal Cancer	https://ClinicalTrials.gov/show/NCT02928224
NCT02657434	A Study of Atezolizumab in Combination With Carboplatin or Cisplatin + Pemetrexed Compared With Carboplatin or Cisplatin + Pemetrexed in Participants Who Are Chemotherapy-Naive and Have Stage IV Non-Squamous Non-Small Cell Lung Cancer (NSCLC) (IMpower 132)	https://ClinicalTrials.gov/show/NCT02657434
NCT02655016	A Study of Niraparib Maintenance Treatment in Patients With Advanced Ovarian Cancer Following Response on Front-Line Platinum-Based Chemotherapy	https://ClinicalTrials.gov/show/NCT02655016
NCT02603432	A Study of Avelumab In Patients With Locally Advanced Or Metastatic Urothelial Cancer (JAVELIN Bladder 100)	https://ClinicalTrials.gov/show/NCT02603432
NCT02718417	Avelumab in Previously Untreated Patients With Epithelial Ovarian Cancer (JAVELIN OVARIAN 100)	https://ClinicalTrials.gov/show/NCT02718417
NCT02768558	Cisplatin and Etoposide Plus Radiation Followed By Nivolumab/Placebo For Locally Advanced NSCLC	https://ClinicalTrials.gov/show/NCT02768558
NCT02677896	A Study of Enzalutamide Plus Androgen Deprivation Therapy (ADT) Versus Placebo Plus ADT in Patients With Metastatic Hormone Sensitive Prostate Cancer (mHSPC)	https://ClinicalTrials.gov/show/NCT02677896
NCT02763566	A Study of Abemaciclib (LY2835219) in Participants With Breast Cancer	https://ClinicalTrials.gov/show/NCT02763566
NCT03125902	A Study of Atezolizumab and Paclitaxel Versus Placebo and Paclitaxel in Participants With Previously Untreated Locally Advanced or Metastatic Triple Negative Breast Cancer (TNBC)	https://ClinicalTrials.gov/show/NCT03125902
NCT03428477	EPA for Metastasis Trial 2	https://ClinicalTrials.gov/show/NCT03428477
NCT02788279	A Study to Investigate Efficacy and Safety of Cobimetinib Plus Atezolizumab and Atezolizumab Monotherapy Versus Regorafenib in Participants With Metastatic Colorectal Adenocarcinoma (COTEZO IMblaze370)	https://ClinicalTrials.gov/show/NCT02788279
NCT02838420	A Study to Evaluate and Compare the Efficacy and Safety of Alectinib Versus Crizotinib and to Evaluate the Pharmacokinetics of Alectinib in Asian Participants With Treatment-Naive Anaplastic Lymphoma Kinase (ALK)-Positive Advanced Non-Small Cell Lung Cancer (NSCLC)	https://ClinicalTrials.gov/show/NCT02838420
NCT02990338	Multinational Clinical Study Comparing Isatuximab, Pomalidomide, and Dexamethasone to Pomalidomide and Dexamethasone in Refractory or Relapsed and Refractory Multiple Myeloma Patients	https://ClinicalTrials.gov/show/NCT02990338
NCT03745222	A Study of Tislelizumab (BGB-A317) Plus Chemoradiotherapy Followed by Tislelizumab Monotherapy in Newly Diagnosed, Stage III Subjects With Locally Advanced, Unresectable Non-small Cell Lung Cancer	https://ClinicalTrials.gov/show/NCT03745222
NCT03351361	Nivolumab and Ipilimumab Versus Chemoimmunotherapy in First Line Treatment in PS 2 or Elderly in Advanced NSCLC Patients	https://ClinicalTrials.gov/show/NCT03351361
NCT02763579	A Study of Carboplatin Plus Etoposide With or Without Atezolizumab in Participants With Untreated Extensive-Stage (ES) Small Cell Lung Cancer (SCLC)	https://ClinicalTrials.gov/show/NCT02763579
NCT02979899	Trial of TRC105 and Pazopanib Versus Pazopanib Alone in Patients With Advanced Angiosarcoma	https://ClinicalTrials.gov/show/NCT02979899
NCT03520959	A Phase 3, Randomized, Double-blind, Placebo-controlled Study For Subjects With Locally-advanced Unresectable or Metastatic Synovial Sarcoma (V943-003, IMDZ-04-1702)	https://ClinicalTrials.gov/show/NCT03520959
NCT03653546	First Line Treatment in EGFR Mutation Positive Advanced NSCLC Patients With Central Nervous System Metastases	https://ClinicalTrials.gov/show/NCT03653546
NCT02631876	A Study of Mirvetuximab Soravtansine vs. Investigator's Choice of Chemotherapy in Women With Folate Receptor (FR) Alpha Positive Advanced Epithelial Ovarian Cancer (EOC), Primary Peritoneal or Fallopian Tube Cancer	https://ClinicalTrials.gov/show/NCT02631876
NCT03069352	A Study of Venetoclax in Combination With Low Dose Cytarabine Versus Low Dose Cytarabine Alone in Treatment Naive Patients With Acute Myeloid Leukemia Who Are Ineligible for Intensive Chemotherapy	https://ClinicalTrials.gov/show/NCT03069352
NCT03158688	Study of Carfilzomib, Daratumumab and Dexamethasone for Patients With Relapsed and/or Refractory Multiple Myeloma.	https://ClinicalTrials.gov/show/NCT03158688
NCT02853331	Study to Evaluate the Efficacy and Safety of Pembrolizumab (MK-3475) in Combination With Axitinib Versus Sunitinib Monotherapy in Participants With Renal Cell Carcinoma (MK-3475-426/KEYNOTE-426)	https://ClinicalTrials.gov/show/NCT02853331

NCT02714218	A Study of Two Different Dose Combinations of Nivolumab in Combination With Ipilimumab in Subjects With Previously Untreated, Unresectable or Metastatic Melanoma	https://ClinicalTrials.gov/show/NCT02714218
NCT02908672	A Study of Atezolizumab Plus Cobimetinib and Vemurafenib Versus Placebo Plus Cobimetinib and Vemurafenib in Previously Untreated BRAFv600 Mutation-Positive Patients With Metastatic or Unresectable Locally Advanced Melanoma	https://ClinicalTrials.gov/show/NCT02908672
NCT03273153	A Study of Cobimetinib Plus Atezolizumab Versus Pembrolizumab in Participants With Previously Untreated Advanced BRAFv600 Wild-Type Melanoma	https://ClinicalTrials.gov/show/NCT03273153
EPARs	Title	URL
Nerlynx	Nerlynx : EPAR - Product Information Procedure No. EMEA/H/C/004030/0000	https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/medicines/human/EPAR/nerlynx#overview
Braftovi	Braftovi : EPAR - Product information Procedure No. EMEA/H/C/004580/0000	https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/medicines/human/EPAR/braftovi
IMFINZI	Imfinzi : EPAR - Product information Procedure No. EMEA/H/C/004771/0000	https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/medicines/human/EPAR/imfinzi
Verzenios - MONARCH 3	Verzenios : EPAR - Product information Procedure No. EMEA/H/C/004302/0000	https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/medicines/human/EPAR/verzenios
Verzenios - MONARCH 2	Verzenios : EPAR - Product information Procedure No. EMEA/H/C/004302/0000	https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/medicines/human/EPAR/verzenios
APEALEA	Apealea : EPAR - Product information Procedure No. EMEA/H/C/004154/0000	https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/medicines/human/EPAR/apealea
POTELIGEO	Poteligeo : EPAR - Product information Procedure No. EMEA/H/C/004232/0000	https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/medicines/human/EPAR/poteligeo
Erleada	Erleada : EPAR - Product information Procedure No. EMEA/H/C/004452/0000	https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/medicines/human/EPAR/erleada
TALZENNA	Talzenna : EPAR - Product information Procedure No. EMEA/H/C/004674/0000	https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/medicines/human/EPAR/talzenna
VIZIMPRO	Vizimpro : EPAR - Product information Procedure No. EMEA/H/C/004779/0000	https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/medicines/human/EPAR/vizimpro
XOSPATA	Xospata : EPAR - Product information Procedure No. EMEA/H/C/004752/0000	https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/medicines/human/EPAR/xospata
NUBEQA	Nubeqa : EPAR - Product information Procedure No. EMEA/H/C/004790/0000	https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/medicines/human/EPAR/nubeqa
Calquence	Calquence : EPAR - Product information Procedure No. EMEA/H/C/005299/0000	https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/medicines/human/EPAR/calquence
Piqray	Piqray : EPAR - Product information Procedure No. EMEA/H/C/004804/0000	https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/medicines/human/EPAR/piqray
Methodological guidelines		
Author	Title	Source
Stephens 2004	The Analysis, Interpretation, and Presentation of Quality of Life Data	https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/15027500/
Osoba 2005	Analysis and interpretation of health-related quality-of-life data from clinical trials: basic approach of The National Cancer Institute of Canada Clinical Trials Group; European Journal of Cancer 41 (2005)	https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/15661554/
Fiero 2020	Demystifying the estimand framework: a case study using patient-reported outcomes in oncology	https://www.thelancet.com/journals/lanonc/article/PIIS1470-2045(20)30319-3/fulltext
Lawrence 2020	What is an estimand & how does it relate to quantifying the effect of treatment on patient-reported quality of life outcomes in clinical trials?	https://jpro.springeropen.com/articles/10.1186/s41687-020-00218-5
Chassany 2002	Patient-Reported Outcomes: The Example of Health-Related Quality of Life—A European Guidance Document for the Improved Integration of Health-Related Quality of Life Assessment in the Drug Regulatory Process	https://doi.org/10.1177%2F009286150203600127
EORTC	Guidelines for assessing Quality of Life in EORTC clinical trials	https://www.eortc.org/app/uploads/sites/2/2018/02/guidelines_for_developing_questionnaire_final.pdf
Bonnetain 2016	Statistical challenges in the analysis of health-related quality of life in cancer clinical trials	https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/27091712/
Coens 2020	International standards for the analysis of quality-of-life and patient-reported outcome endpoints in cancer randomised controlled trials: recommendations of the SISAQOL Consortium	
Calvert 2018	Guidelines for Inclusion of Patient-Reported Outcomes in Clinical Trial Protocols The SPIRIT-PRO Extension	https://jamanetwork.com/journals/jama/article-abstract/2671472
Calvert 2013	Reporting of Patient-Reported Outcomes in Randomized Trials The CONSORT PRO Extension	https://jamanetwork.com/journals/jama/fullarticle/1656259
Brundage 2012	Patient-reported outcomes in randomized clinical trials: development of ISOQOL reporting standards	https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s1136-012-0252-1
Nayfield 1992	Report from National Cancer Institute (USA) workshop on the Quality of Life assessment in cancer clinical trials	
Stakeholder guidelines		
Author	Title	URL
FDA 2018	PFDD Guidance 3 (public workshop): Patient-Focused Drug Development Guidance: Methods to Identify What is Important to Patients and Select, Develop or Modify Fit-for-Purpose Clinical Outcome Assessments	https://www.fda.gov/media/116277/download

FDA 2019	PFDD Guidance 4 (public workshop): Patient-Focused Drug Development: Guidance 4 – Incorporating Clinical Outcome Assessments into Endpoints for Regulatory Decision Making	https://www.fda.gov/media/132505/download
FDA 2019b	Public workshop on PFDD: Incorporating Clinical Outcome Assessments into Endpoints for Regulatory Decision Making	https://www.fda.gov/media/133891/download
FDA 2009	FDA guidance for industry: Patient-Reported Outcome Measures: Use in Medical Product Development to Support Labeling Claims	https://www.fda.gov/media/77832/download
FDA2018b	Clinical Trial Endpoints for the Approval of Cancer Drugs and Biologics Guidance for Industry	https://www.fda.gov/media/71195/download
FDA 2019c	COA-CCT Session III Using a standardized estimand framework for medical product review and labelling: a case study	https://www.fda.gov/media/132102/download
EMA 2016	Appendix 2 to the guideline on the evaluation of anticancer medicinal products in man - the use of patient-reported outcome (PRO) measures in oncology studies	https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/documents/other/appendix-2-guideline-evaluation-anticancer-medicinal-products-man_en.pdf
EMA 2005	EMA (European Medicines Agency), Committee for Medicinal Products for Human Use. 2005. Reflection paper on the regulatory guidance for us of health-related quality of life (HRQOL) measures in the evaluation of medicinal products. European Medicines	https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/documents/scientific-guideline/reflection-paper-regulatory-guidance-use-healthrelated-quality-life-hrql-measures-evaluation_en.pdf
EMA 2019	Guideline on the clinical evaluation of anticancer medicinal products	https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/documents/scientific-guideline/draft-guideline-evaluation-anticancer-medicinal-products-man-revision-6_en.pdf
HTA (EUnetHTA) 2015	Endpoints used for Relative Effectiveness Assessment: Clinical Endpoints	https://eunetha.eu/wp-content/uploads/2018/02/WP7-SG3-GL-clin_endpoints_amend2015.pdf
HTA (EUnetHTA) 2013	Endpoints used for relative effectiveness assessment of pharmaceuticals. HEALTH-RELATED QUALITY OF LIFE and UTILITY MEASURES	https://eunetha.eu/wp-content/uploads/2013/01/Health-related-quality-of-life.pdf
HTA (IQWiG) 2020	IQWiG methods paper version 6.0	https://www.iqwig.de/en/about-us/methods/methods-paper/